

Terms of Reference for the College of Medicine and Health Research and Innovation Subcommittee for Research Integrity

Background

Supporting and developing a culture of research integrity at UCC is vital to our strategic plan (2023-2028), *Securing Our Future*¹. Our commitment to integrity demands that research is methodologically rigorous, conducted to the highest ethical standards, and protects the accuracy of the scientific record. It also demands that research misconduct is dealt with appropriately, and that the approaches for assessing research and researchers are not a detriment to research integrity. Efforts to support research integrity are closely aligned with concerns about research waste² and the reproducibility of research, Irish and EU policies in support of open research⁴; and the stated priorities of national, European and international research funders.

Our existing commitment to research integrity at UCC is reflected in the UCC Researcher Code of Conduct⁵, existing training programmes in research integrity⁶, and a Research Data Management Policy aimed at facilitating high quality research and research integrity⁷. Many academics at UCC are also signatories to the Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)⁸, and UCC as an institution is a signatory to the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA)⁹, a member of the National Research Integrity Forum (NRIF)¹⁰, and subscribes to the UK Research Integrity Office (UKRIO)¹¹.

Building on these existing endeavours and investments, the UCC Strategic Plan (2023-2028) affirms UCC's ambition "to be the leading university in Ireland for research and innovation, based on a reputation for discovery, research integrity and sustainability". Our ambitions to develop and maintain a reputation for research integrity are particularly clear in Strategic Approach 1.4: *Transform UCC's research culture through the implementation of engaged research and open research underpinned by academic integrity, and ethical and responsible practice*. To support these ambitions, the College of Medicine and Health Research and Innovation Committee (CoMH RIC) will establish a Subcommittee on Research Integrity (SRI), focusing on the following interest areas: open research; research data management and stewardship; training in ethics and research integrity; evaluation of research and researchers; and methodological rigor.

Aims of the CoMH RIC Subcommittee for Research Integrity

The overarching aim of the SRI will be to support the CoMH RIC in its efforts to address the UCC Strategy (2023-2028), Strategic Approach 1.4, particularly with respect to Priority Actions ii, iv, and v:

- ii. Develop policies and mechanisms to support the effective dissemination of research expertise and maximise impact by taking a coordinated, holistic approach to embedding principles and practices of open research.
- iv. Provide support to ensure FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data stewardship.
- v. Ensure that the environment in UCC supports the conduct of research to the highest ethical standards, and that UCC researchers are appropriately trained.

The SRI will also aim to support the CoMH RIC meet its terms of reference by helping to ensure “that the infrastructure and supports are available and visible in the CoMH that supports a culture of engaged research and open research, academic integrity, and that support ethical and responsible practice and support that EDI [equality, diversity and inclusion] is enshrined in the CoMH”¹² (noting that Engaged Research and EDI will be the focus of separate CoMH committees).

Notably, the SRI will not play any role in the work of ethics committees or UCC processes for dealing with research misconduct.

Activities

To support its aims, the SRI will:

- Regularly signpost and summarize relevant resources and events for the wider College.
- Host informal research integrity meetups on campus.
- Organize seminars on research integrity for the wider College.
- Consider specific, actionable requests for information and/or recommendations from the CoMH RIC.
- Horizon-scan for risks to research integrity and when appropriate make recommendations to the CoMH RIC to correct, mitigate or avoid them.
- Suggest actions aimed at promoting the responsible conduct of research and fostering a culture embracing research integrity within CoMH.

To support these activities, the SRI will meet as a group three times a year (Fall, Spring, Summer). Meetings will be held online and organized by the SRI chair.

Membership

The membership of the CoMH SRI will include representation across its constituent schools, research centres, and other key institutions within UCC (including, but not limited to, the OVPRI, the research integrity office, relevant ethics committees, IT services, and UCC Library). The SRI will also aim to include members across career paths and stages, including research students; and broadly reflect the sociodemographic diversity of staff and students in the CoMH. Staff members will agree to serve for at least one 2-year term starting in September, while student members will agree to serve at least one 1-year term. All members can serve up to a maximum of 3 consecutive terms. The chair will rotate every 2 years. As members leave the SRI, they will be asked to nominate a replacement for consideration by the SRI and will be approved to join via consensus.

Reporting

The SRI Chair will report on the activities of the SRI to the CoMH RIC at its regular meetings.

References

1. Securing Our Futures: UCC Strategic Plan (2023-2028)
<https://www.ucc.ie/en/president/strategy2028/>
2. Research: increasing value, reducing waste <https://www.thelancet.com/series/research>
3. A manifesto for reproducible science <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41562-016-0021>
4. National Open Research Forum <https://norf.ie/>
5. UCC Researcher Code of Conduct.
<https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/research/researchatucc/researchsupports/researchintegrity/UCCCodeofResearchConductV2.4-approved14thSeptember2021.pdf>
6. Research Integrity @ UCC
<https://www.ucc.ie/en/research/support/integrity/aboutresearchintegrityucc/>
7. Research Data Management Policy, V 0.6 (June 2024)
<https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/research/researchatucc/researchculture/policiesproceduresandguidelines/UCCResearchDataManagementPolicy.pdf>

8. The Declaration on Research Assessment <https://sfdora.org/>
9. Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment <https://coara.eu/>
10. National Research Integrity Forum <https://www.iua.ie/for-researchers/research-integrity/>
11. UK Research Integrity Office <https://ukrio.org/>
12. UCC College of Medicine and Health Research & Innovation Committee – Terms of Reference

Appendices

Current membership (AY 2024/25-2025/26)

- Darren Dahly (Chair) - Senior Lecturer, School of Public Health; Principal Statistician, Clinical Research Facility
- Karen Matvienko-Sikar - Senior Lecturer-, School of Public Health
- Brendan Palmer - Manager of Research Data Services, Clinical Research Facility
- Aoife Coffey - Research Data Coordinator, UCC Library
- Christian Waeber - Professor, School of Pharmacy; Chair, Animal Experimentation Ethics Committee
- Caitriona O'Driscoll - Professor, School of Pharmacy
- Robert Callaghan - PhD student, School of Pharmacy
- John Browne - Professor, School of Public Health
- Elaine Lehane - Senior Lecturer, School of Nursing & Midwifery
- Irene Kavanagh - Research Officer, Research Integrity & Research Culture Support UCC Research-OVPRI
- Jerry Deasy - Research IT Lead at College of Medicine
- Pauline Frizelle - Senior Lecturer, School of Clinical Therapies
- Ken O'Halloran - Professor, School of Medicine; UCC Research Integrity Officer
- Joye McKernon - Research Officer, National Perinatal Epidemiology Centre
- Noeleen Brady - Senior Research Coordinator, School of Nursing & Midwifery
- Sebastian Dohm-Hansen - PhD Student, School of Medicine
- Yensi Flores Bueso - Postdoctoral Researcher, School of Medicine; CoARA Steering Board Member
- Mairead Harding - Professor, School of Dentistry

Ex officio membership

Gerard O'Keeffe (CoMH RIC Chair)